

Representation of Coherent Structures from Volume Data Using Quality-oriented Features and Genetic Optimization

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Abstract—Representing relevant information from volume data sets is a problem often faced in visualization. Generating meaningful images from highly-complex volume data sets is a challenging, tedious task requiring specialized knowledge of the distribution and properties of the data. Traditionally, this task has been carried out manually via specialized user interfaces. We propose a volume visualization pipeline which facilitates the automatic generation of high-quality images from volume data sets. Our method involves a direct volume renderer which generates images from volume data based on visual mappings provided by a transfer function. Central to our approach is a quality-focused descriptor which exploits the properties of the distribution of gradient orientations of an alpha-bounded surface within the volume. This feature is useful for determining transfer functions that result in the rendering of corresponding images depicting various details from the volume. We show that by using this feature as an optimization objective, the generation of high quality images can be automated. Using simple genetic algorithms, we can automatically generate sets of images illustrating coherent, easily-distinguishable and high-quality surfaces of relevant structures from volume data.

Keywords— *volume rendering, information visualization, quality surface features, evolutionary optimization*

I. INTRODUCTION

Volume rendering is an essential technique in scientific visualization that enables the understanding and analysis of complex volumetric data. In recent years, the growing availability of high-resolution 3D scanning and imaging technologies has greatly increased the amount and complexity of volumetric data. As a result, the demand for efficient and effective volume rendering techniques has also increased significantly.

One of the key challenges in volume rendering is to generate visualizations that are both informative and visually appealing. Informative visualizations should provide a clear and accurate representation of the underlying data, while visually appealing visualizations should be aesthetically pleasing and easy to understand. To address this issue, it is important to have proper quality or diversity criteria that can guide the rendering process. Quality criteria are used to evaluate the accuracy and fidelity of the rendered images, while diversity criteria are used to ensure that the images are diverse and cover a wide range of possible visualizations. However, manually defining and optimizing these criteria is a complex and time-consuming task, which limits the scalability and efficiency of the rendering process. Therefore,

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there is a need for automatic methods that can optimize these criteria and generate diverse and informative volume renderings without manual intervention.

In this paper, our main objective is to facilitate the automatic generation of diverse image sets which illustrate various coherently-represented objects and structures from volume data. To this end, we propose an automated data visualization pipeline for generating images from complex volume data sets. The pipeline consists of a volume renderer that explores and samples the volume using a volume ray caster and transfer function, a metric that can be used to assess the quality of resulting images, and an automated procedure of generating a collection of images using a genetic algorithm that optimizes the metric. This quality descriptor allows for the generation of images containing coherent and well-defined structures and objects from the volume data. We use a chi-squared score as a fitness function to assess the uniformness of the distribution of gradient orientations with respect to alpha-bounded surfaces. The results show that maximizing this criterion leads to transfer functions that allow for rendering images of objects and volumetric structures with coherent surfaces. The proposed method offers a means of automated image generation that can produce diverse and suitable visualizations. To our knowledge, such an approach has not been used before for this type of data, considering the complexity of displaying easily-interpretable structures from volumes.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II presents multiple relevant results from the related literature; in Section III we provide a brief description of the visualization problem addressed in the paper, and relevant context information in support of our objectives; Section IV contains a detailed description of our approach and its main components; in Section V we present and interpret the results of our work, obtained experimentally using our method; the paper ends with a final section where we provide concluding remarks and details concerning future work.

II. RELATED WORK

A review of literature on volume rendering techniques for feature enhancement is presented in [1]. It identifies four categories of approaches based on the enhancement of external, internal, structural, and ideographic features and two patterns: property enhancement volume rendering focuses on visual mapping, while perception enhancement volume rendering focuses on interactive visualization design.

Various quality metrics for information visualization are reviewed in [2], with a focus on measuring clutter, overlap, and visual patterns. The authors organize the reviewed papers by five data types of information visualization: multi-/high-dimensional, relational, geospatial, sequential/temporal, and text data. They find that the major research developments in the field are increasingly focusing on visual pattern retrieval rather than pure clutter reduction approaches. One of their main contributions is the formalization, unification, and exemplification of the major quality metric vocabulary, which may enable more structured work on the problem.

The authors of [3] present a systematization of techniques that use quality metrics to support the exploration of high-dimensional data sets. They analyze visualization approaches, quality metrics, and the processing pipeline, and derive a set of factors for discriminating the quality metrics.

A method called NeuS is described in [4] for high-fidelity surface reconstruction of objects and scenes from 2D image inputs. Other methods for surface reconstruction struggle with severe self-occlusion or thin structures, while recent neural methods for novel view synthesis use volume rendering to produce a neural scene representation, but have difficulty extracting high-quality surfaces.

An automated method for 3D visualization of brain tumors is presented in [5]. The method consists of two main steps that are fully automated. In the first step, segmentation is applied to each slice of volume data using the FCPN method [6]. In the second step, ray casting is employed for 3D volume rendering using the data processed in the first step. Thus, the proposed two-step method uses segmentation to highlight coherent structures during volume rendering. To overcome the drawback of supervised learning, other researchers have approached different clustering methods for 3D image segmentation [7-10], a popular technique is the Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) [11].

A semi-automatic 3D feature extraction and visualization method is proposed in [12], which is based on GMM. The manual intervention consists of choosing two slices of volume data, and the features of interest must be selected and labeled. Then, the two slices with the selected features are used to automatically extract the 3D features from the volume data using GMM. The final 3D view can be further adjusted by manual intervention. In [13] a fully automated method is proposed for the segmentation and 3D visualization of lesions from whole breast ultrasound images. In the first step, the volume of interest is automatically selected, and a 3D level set method is used. The obtained volume is preprocessed in the second step to remove the speckled noise and the shadowing artifacts. The segmentation is performed in the third step, where a) the first volume slice is used to define a seed point position automatically, and b) a level set method is iteratively used on subsequent slices. In the last step, isosurface rendering is used for 3D visualization of the lesions.

Although using clustering techniques helps to automate the segmentation of 3D objects, these techniques may miss essential features from volume data. Researchers have focused on improving volumetric rendering techniques without relying on intermediate geometric polygonal elements, and direct volume rendering (DVR) techniques are of great interest. Specifically, DVR ray casting is important in many research areas and is superior to other GPU-accelerated methods [14]. Ray casting uses parallel rays sent through volume data to obtain a two-dimensional projection. The main component

uses a transfer function that maps voxels sampled along the ray into a single pixel with different colors and opacities. To obtain a projection with coherent structures, designing a transfer function is a very important task in DVR research [15]. Also, the ray casting technique can be accelerated using a ray termination criterion based on empty space skipping or early ray termination. Different optimization schemes can be used, even in web applications. Since visualization quality is subjective to the user, automatically evaluating the quality of rendered volumes is a challenge. For this reason, confidence in visualization quality metrics is sometimes supported by subjective user studies [16-18]. An automated process for providing a suitable visualization of volume data is proposed in [16]. Treemaps are used as a case study for volume data visualization. The problem is to find the most suitable treemap that best describes the volume data in terms of perceptual properties. An evolutionary algorithm is employed to evolve suitable treemaps, where the properties of a single treemap are encoded in a fixed-length chromosome. A similar finding is demonstrated in [17], where the linear combination of two metrics is a better quality assessment for rendered 3D models. The finding in the latter work is supported by a subjective assessment from over one hundred participants. The work of [18] shows the importance of quality assessment for rendered 3D point clouds, where an extensive performance evaluation is conducted using thirteen quality assessment models. The authors also propose a new assessment model that performs significantly better, and the results are supported by a subjective user study with sixteen participants.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

Our method involves the automated generation of images from complex volume data sets using an appropriately-designed spatial and data-based feature. Volume data may originate from a wide range of sources, including medical scanning devices, radar / LiDAR, or industrial computerized tomography (CT) and ultrasound. Such data is generally of high complexity and contain multiple structures and geometric features, some of which provide meaningful information on the specifics of the data, and some of which are the result of noise or the fusion of multiple unrelated objects. We define *coherent structures* as subsets of the data set which can be represented via clearly-defined, relatively-continuous surfaces which are easy to interpret visually, and which allow for the fast visual identification of the most relevant geometric features contained within the data set. Fig. 1 provides examples and counter-examples of such representations, originating from a medical CT data set. Volume data typically contains values which are the direct result of the method used for their acquisition, for example, values indicating the absorption coefficients of specific electromagnetic frequencies. We typically refer to such values as *densities*, considering that in many scenarios they represent a density-related physical property of the corresponding region of space (such as tissue density in the case of medical CT). When generating images from such data, the challenge is determining a relevant relationship between density values and visual properties (color and opacity). This is typically achieved by defining and manipulating a transfer function, which constitutes a mapping from the domain of the volume data to the RGBA color space. Consequently, by defining a function $f: D \rightarrow [0, 1]^4$, which generates an RGBA quadruplet for any value from density domain D , one can control the distribution of colors and opacities throughout the volume. Consequently, different transfer functions can highlight

different structures, features or objects from the data set. The problem is defining transfer functions for which the corresponding color and opacity mappings result in meaningful, quality representations of objects and structures of interest. By *quality*, we mean that the surfaces of the highlighted objects are relatively continuous and clearly delineated, such that the corresponding objects are easy to distinguish and interpret visually, as exemplified in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Examples of images generated from a CT data set, illustrating objects with: (a) coherent, well-identified surfaces; (b) discontinuous, fragmented and noisy surfaces.

This is traditionally done manually or, at most, semi-automatically, through specialized user interfaces. Adjusting the transfer function via such interfaces is not a straightforward task, requiring some beforehand knowledge of the data set, its density distribution and other particularities. An automated means of determining such functions is often preferred, such that volume visualization is made more straightforward and accessible to a broader range of users. Our contribution is the formulation of an automated volume visualization pipeline, involving a feature extraction method which constitutes an objective characterization of quality that allows for fast generation of meaningful image sets from volume data using genetic algorithms.

IV. METHOD DESCRIPTION

Our approach consists in an automated data visualization pipeline which can be broken down into the following components: a volume renderer which generates images from volume data using a volume ray caster to explore and sample the volume and a transfer function to assign color and opacity to the resulting samples; a means of computing a feature which accounts for the quality of the resulting images; an automated means of generating a collection of images by optimizing said feature using a genetic algorithm. The general functionality is illustrated in the diagram from Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Diagram of the main components and functionality of the described method.

A. Volume Renderer

We use an image rendering method based on a direct volume ray caster [19]. Ray casting is a means of exploring and sampling the volume data set, such that a high-enough number of sufficiently-representative samples is collected in order to properly cover both the spatial extent of the volume, and its value domain. The general approach of a volume ray caster is illustrated in Fig. 3. From each pixel, a ray is projected through the volume data set, and multiple samples

are determined per ray. Initially, the samples do not have intrinsic optical properties, since they consist in linearly-interpolated values from the data set. Subsequently, a transfer function is used to assign RGBA values to the samples, which are then combined per ray to form colors for their corresponding pixels. As a result, an image is generated where each pixel color is determined by integrating the sample colors along the corresponding ray, weighed by their respective opacities.

Fig. 3. Illustration of volume ray casting: for any pixel, a ray is projected through the volume data set; samples are collected along the ray and color values are assigned to the samples via a transfer function. The final color of the pixel results from combining the colors of the samples along the ray.

For any pixel, the accumulated color C results from compositing the colors C_i and opacities A_j for samples i taken along the corresponding ray of the pixel, as described in the discrete volume rendering equation (Eq. 1). We denote i as the index of the samples along the ray, $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$, where N is the number of samples taken along the ray until a ray termination criterion is reached (such as when the ray has exited the volume bounding geometry or when the accumulated alpha has reached a threshold very close to 1.0).

$$C = \sum_{i=1}^N C_i \prod_{j=1}^{i-1} (1 - A_j) \quad (1)$$

$$A = 1 - \prod_{j=1}^N (1 - A_j)$$

For sample i with data value d_i , the corresponding color components $C_i = (R_i, G_i, B_i)$ and opacity A_i result from applying transfer function $f: D \rightarrow [0, 1]^4$, such that $f(d_i) = (R_i, G_i, B_i, A_i)$. We define the transfer function as a piecewise 3rd degree spline, where each component is defined as $f: [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $f(u) = -2u^3 + 3u^2$, a particular case of Hermite polynomial commonly known as a *smoothstep* function [20] (Fig. 4.). The bounding points of each smoothstep piece are the *control points* of the transfer function. By specifying and altering these control points, the shape of the function changes and, consequently, so does the distribution of color and opacity within the volume. Within the space of possible transfer functions, a subset exists which results in meaningful representations of relevant structures from the data set. As such, a proper exploration of this space is necessary, as well as obtaining usable transfer function candidates through appropriately-chosen optimization objectives.

Fig. 4. Representation of a transfer function defined as a piecewise 3rd degree polynomial, where each component is a control point-bounded smoothstep function. The horizontal axis represents the domain of the volume data set (the unit of measurement depends on the actual data and the acquisition method); the vertical axis is the opacity domain (adimensional). Color values are also defined for each control point and interpolated.

B. Feature Extraction for Quality Image Generation

In order to automate the image rendering process, we propose a quality descriptor that, when used as optimization objective, allows the generation of images containing meaningful, coherent structures and objects from the volume data. We consider a *quality image* one where the displayed structures have cohesive, well defined surfaces, and their spatial properties are easy to interpret visually. Within a volume data set the notion of *surface* is not well-defined. A *surface* is a subset of volume samples that is chosen according to a criterion that achieves the desired objective with regard to the resulting visual representation. We define an *alpha-bounded surface* as the subset of samples where the accumulated opacity along the corresponding ray reaches a predefined threshold. Therefore, an alpha-bounded surface is formed from the samples along each ray where $A = A_T$. (Fig. 5) For our purposes, we set this threshold to $A_T = 0.7$, an opacity which is a good value to indicate the point at which the corresponding structures start to become clearly visible [21]. This surface is not necessarily the bounding surface of an object from the data set, but it generally defines the border at which the volume structures are clearly visible, regardless of the actual objects they represent. At each sample along this surface, we compute the dot product between the normalized gradient vector and the vector indicating the direction of the observer (the viewing direction), therefore at each sample we obtain the orientation of the gradient with respect to the viewer (Fig. 5). Our descriptor is based on the analysis of the distribution of these orientations. The general idea is that a smoother, more coherent surface will have gradients with fewer orientations, whose distribution will therefore be less uniform. Conversely, a rougher surface consisting in more geometric features (and possibly more noise) will result in a “flatter” gradient orientation, i.e., one which is closer to uniform. We refer to this property as the *uniformness* of the distribution. A distribution with less uniformness will deviate from the uniform distribution more than one with higher uniformness. We can easily measure this property by determining the chi-squared score between the resulting distribution and the equivalent uniform one. Gradient vectors at a bounding surface within a volume space are analogous to surface normals in traditional polygonal-based raster graphics, or for any well-defined surface, in general. Therefore, the shape of the distribution of gradient orientations can generally be interpreted as follows:

- a distribution with low uniformness is indicative of bounding surfaces which are relatively flat and do not exhibit a great deal of variation in their geometry, curvature or spatial features;
- a highly-uniform distribution is indicative of a surface with many spatial features (i.e., many curved variation, bumps, ridges, valleys, etc.), but it may very well indicate a fragmented, discontinuous and/or noisy surface.

This interpretation allows us to derive a criterion for generating objects such that their surfaces are continuous and coherent, as opposed to broken up, fragmented or too visually complex. A high chi-squared score usually corresponds to objects with smoother, simpler, clearly distinguishable surfaces, while a lower score indicates surfaces with more spatial features but that may not be as visually relevant or easily interpretable. However, an alpha-bounded surface does not implicitly represent the outline of a distinctive structure

within the volume, but rather the boundary at which all structures, generally, start becoming visible. Consequently, we do not aim to directly represent alpha-bounded surfaces, but rather use their orientation with respect to the viewer as a criterion for generating color and opacity mappings that expose important objects and structures. By experimenting with this criterion, we found that these objects and structures tend to have coherently-outlined surfaces when the criterion is maximized.

Fig. 5. Determining gradient orientation: along any ray, at the sampling point where the accumulated opacity A reaches threshold A_T , the gradient orientation is the dot product between gradient G and viewing vector V .

C. Genetic Optimization

In order to automatically identify objects with clearly-delineated surfaces, we use a genetic algorithm to explore the transfer function space. Considering the definition of such a function described in Section IV, the transfer function space is reduced to $N \times [0,1]^5$, i.e. the space of the control points that represent the borders of each smoothstep component. N is the number of control points, and $[0,1]^5$ is the value domain of an individual control point. Specifically, this is the domain of values $[D, R, G, B, A]$, which are the data value, color and opacity components specified for a control point. Considering this, we define the chromosome to be used within the genetic algorithm as real valued vector $[D_1, R_1, G_1, B_1, A_1, D_2, R_2, G_2, B_2, A_2, \dots, D_N, R_N, G_N, B_N, A_N]$, where D_i, R_i, G_i, B_i, A_i are the data value, red, green, blue and opacity values of control point i , respectively. This means that the purpose of the genetic algorithm is to search for transfer functions which are formed from smoothstep components defined by N control points, such that any data value d is associated with an RGBA quadruplet. For each such transfer function, an image may be rendered which is the result of the color and opacity mapping provided by the respective transfer function. We define the fitness function as the previously-mentioned chi-squared score, which assesses the uniformness of the distribution of the gradient orientations with respect to the alpha-bounded surface resulting from the mapping of the transfer function. Considering that the probability histogram of gradient orientations is determined over N_H bins, where the histogram value h_i in each bin i is the probability that the dot product between the viewing vector and the gradient vector falls within $[i/N_H, (i+1)/N_H]$, $i = 0 \dots N_H-1$, the optimization objective involves maximizing the chi-squared score between the distribution described by the probability histogram and the equivalent uniform distribution defined by the histogram average \bar{h} (Eq. 2).

$$\chi^2 = \frac{\sum_{i=0}^{N_H-1} (h_i - \bar{h})^2}{\bar{h}} \quad (2)$$

We find that maximizing this criterion generally results in transfer functions which allow the rendering of images depicting objects and volumetric structures with coherent surfaces. The optimizer consists in a genetic algorithm involving the classic steps of such an approach: initialization of the population; evaluation of individuals using the

aforementioned fitness criterion; selection of fittest individuals; crossover and mutation. We use the following genetic algorithm parameters: population size: 30-40; tournament selection with $k=2$; uniform crossover and mutation operators; crossover probability: 0.9; mutation probability: 0.5.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Our experiments consist in generating collections of images using transfer functions obtained via genetic optimization. For each transfer function, we determine its corresponding fitness by first generating a map of gradient orientations with regard to the alpha-bounded surface determined within the volume. Then, we compute the distribution of these orientations and perform the chi-squared test of the distribution against the uniform distribution defined by its median value. We found that the resulting scores determined the extent to which the related transfer functions generated images conforming to our definition of quality when used within a volume renderer. Transfer functions corresponding to high chi-squared scores tend to result in images of objects and structures with smooth, continuous and well-defined surfaces, albeit at the risk of also highlighting less interesting surface features with fewer details (Fig. 6 a,b)). Transfer functions corresponding to low chi-squared scores tend to favor images where the displayed structures exhibit more details and spatial features, however this may also result in noisy, fragmented and/or partial surfaces (Fig. 6 c,d)).

Fig. 6. Images generated from a medical CT data set and the corresponding gradient orientation distributions: (a,b) distributions with low-uniformness tend to favor cleaner images containing objects with coherent surfaces; (c,d) “flatter”, high-uniformness distributions result in images displaying fragmented surfaces and/or objects with increased surface variation and detail but with many discontinuities and noise. Since the depicted graphs illustrate distributions of dot product values, both axes are adimensional.

Considering the above findings, we design our optimizer to maximize the previously-mentioned score. Specifically, we are interested in images with clearly-defined surfaces, at the expense of penalizing more intricately-detailed ones. We randomly initialize a population of transfer functions and then

select / combine / mutate them within a genetic algorithm, using the chi score as the fitness function. Multiple examples of the resulting images are shown in Fig. 7, using three different volume data sets. We found that using a simple genetic algorithm with random uniform mutation and crossover operators, and a tournament selection strategy is enough to generate high-quality results from a population of 30-40 initial transfer functions within a few dozen generations at most. We noticed no obvious benefits from other crossover/mutation operators and no clear increase in diversity when using larger populations. Upon convergence, the resulting transfer function population generally produces images which conform to the previously-described definitions of quality.

Fig. 7. Examples of images obtained using our method, originating from: (a) a 3D CT medical scan; (b) a meteorological radar scan depicting the atmospheric parameters during a hurricane; (c) a 3D model of a scanned bonsai.

Our experiments show that the generation of a collection of high-quality images is not always consistent with optimizing a single objective. While the last population of transfer functions yield visually-relevant images, when little variation is introduced into the population, the optimizer tends to converge to results showing the same surface or, at most, the same few surfaces. In order to encourage some level of diversity within the resulting image collection, we use relatively high crossover and mutation probabilities (0.9 and 0.5, respectively). While this is sufficient for the purposes of the current paper, we will experiment with other means of introducing diversity in future work. One particular downside of our current approach stems from the definition of the automatic image generation task as a single-objective optimization problem. This formulation implies that there exists a “best” image which the evolutionary optimizer converges towards, when in fact the broader objective is to

generate diverse image sets. Therefore, in future versions of this project we intend to experiment with other, more suitable optimization methods which have means of generating “best populations” instead of “the best solution”, as well as built-in mechanisms for ensuring and controlling population diversity. Maximizing the criterion described in Section IV.C may result in transfer functions which result in very noisy gradient orientation distributions. These are exceptional cases which manifest in 5-10% of the generated images. We can counter this effect by imposing constraints of the density domain of the data set, such that higher density structures, where this problem generally manifests, are emphasized more rarely. This does not place a significant constraint on the generated images, since the structures with densities at the extremities of the data value domain are rarely of interest.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

We developed a method for automatically generating visually-relevant images from volume data. We considered quality images those that display coherent, easily-distinguishable surfaces of the most significant objects and structures from the volume data. The main problem for such a task is defining a transfer function which maps the data values of the volume to visual properties, so that the resulting color and opacity distributions allow the rendering of high quality images. To this extent, we defined a descriptor that serves as a metric for generating useful transfer functions. This descriptor was based on identifying an alpha-bounded surface from within the volume for a specific alpha threshold, and then determining the distribution of the orientations of the gradients at the interface defined by this surface. This distribution served to assess the smoothness of the variety of geometric features of such a surface. We measured this property by determining the chi-squared score between the distribution and the equivalent uniform distribution, which constituted a metric for the “flatness” or the amount of equalization of the distribution. We used this criterion as the optimization objective for a genetic algorithm: specifically, the genetic algorithm searched through the transfer function space while maximizing the criterion. Our results so far showed that even a simple genetic algorithm can result in sets of quality images from the final population of transfer functions. The obtained images generally showed coherent, well-structured objects, though we found that a single optimization criterion is far from enough for a complete exploration of the volume. As such, we identified several directions where there is ample room for improvement, which we will address in future work: currently we only use a single criterion to identify structures in the volume data, which, while allowing for the generation of images which conform to our definition of quality, is not enough for identifying more subtle, lower-profile structures; We currently do not handle image diversity in an explicit manner, but rather we encourage diversity in the populations of the genetic algorithm by adjusting its hyperparameters accordingly. Thus, our methods will be extended with metrics that target diversity explicitly. Also, in future work we intend to account for viewing parameters such as the viewer position and direction, so that images from different viewer perspectives can be generated.

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